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Review Article

The Alchemy of Rosemary from Herb Garden to Apothecary: A Comprehensive Pharmaceutical Review

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ABSTRACT

Traditionally used as a culinary herb, Rosemary (*Rosmarinus officinalis*) has recently drawn recognition for its therapeutic qualities in today's health-conscious society. Rosemary has gained attention due to its diverse medicinal properties, which are supported by scientific researches, as more people turn to natural therapies. The antibacterial, neuroprotective, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant qualities of rosemary are highlighted in this study of its possible medical uses. These impacts have important management implications for metabolic illnesses, intestinal problems, cardiovascular health, and cognitive difficulties. Along with discussing potential adverse effects and contraindications, the article also looks at the herb's safety profile. The adaptability of rosemary in both traditional and modern medicine is further illustrated by the discussion of its versatility across a range of forms, including essential oils, extracts, and teas. The study concluded that the health benefits of rosemary herb are enhanced by the synergistic contributions of its active ingredients. Because of its adaptability, the plant can be used in conjunction with a variety of therapies, contributing both therapeutic and antioxidant benefits. Making the connection between the herb's growing use in contemporary medicine and its culinary roots, this review underscores rosemary's growing importance as a natural solution in today's wellness-focused society.

INTRODUCTION

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), health includes physical, mental, and social well-being. Concerns regarding synthetic

drug side effects and the desire for natural health methods have led to an increase in interest in herbal medicine, despite the availability of synthetic pharmaceuticals. [1] [2] [3].

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Image 9: Comprehensive overview of rosemary

Rosemary (*Rosmarinus officinalis*), a medicinal and aromatic herb from the Lamiaceae family, has been valued for its health benefits and culinary uses for centuries. The bioactive compounds responsible for its therapeutic properties include polyphenols such as carnosol, carnosic acid, and rosmarinic acid, along with essential oils like α -pinene, camphor, and eucalyptol. These compounds contribute to rosemary's anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and antimicrobial effects, making it popular in natural remedies. Rosemary can be used in various forms—fresh, dried, as a tea infusion, or as essential oil—and is widely employed in aromatherapy, food preservation, and medical treatments. The plant itself is an evergreen shrub, native to the Mediterranean, and is known for its ability to thrive in drought and withstand cold temperatures. It grows up to 1.8 meters and produces flowers in shades of white, pink, purple, or blue. Due to these properties, rosemary continues to be a key focus in

both traditional medicine and modern health research. [4].

Fig: 1 *Rosmarinus officinalis*

Phytochemistry Of Rosemary

Rosemary (*Rosmarinus officinalis*) is a powerful herb with a wide range of medicinal uses since it is abundant in bioactive chemicals. Polyphenols, terpenoids, flavonoids, and essential oils are among its main constituents, and they all contribute to its wide range of pharmacological actions. A summary of the main types of phytochemicals present in rosemary is shown below:

Phytochemical Group	Compound	Properties	Structure
Polyphenols	Rosmarinic acid	Anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties. Neutralizes free radicals, lowers oxidative stress, and protects cells from harm.	

	Carnosic acid	Potent antioxidant with neuroprotective, anti-inflammatory, and anticancer qualities.	
	Carnosol	Potent antioxidant that contributes to rosemary's defence against oxidative damage.	
Essential oils	Cineole	Antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, and bronchodilator. Included in rosemary essential oil, used in disinfectants and respiratory remedies.	
	Camphor	Known for stimulant, analgesic, and anti-inflammatory properties. Used to relieve pain and provides rosemary's distinctive scent.	
	α -Pinene	Neuroprotective, bronchodilator, and anti-inflammatory. Contributes to rosemary's fragrance and therapeutic properties in the essential oil.	
Flavonoids	Luteolin	Antioxidant, antibacterial, and anti-inflammatory. Modulates immune responses and protects cells	

		from oxidative stress.	
	Apigenin	Anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and potential anticancer properties. Investigated for preventing neurodegenerative disorders.	

Table summarizing the key bioactive compounds in rosemary with their properties and structures. [5], [6]
Importance Of Rosemary And Its Properties

Rosemary's many medicinal uses and qualities make it an important part of contemporary herbal medicine. An outline of its significance is provided below:

Fig: 2 Property of Rosemary

The European Union has approved rosemary extract as a natural antioxidant for use in meat and fish products, recognizing its ability to inhibit lipid oxidation and extend shelf life. This authorization highlights the growing trend of incorporating natural additives to enhance food quality and safety while reducing reliance on synthetic preservatives. The antioxidant properties of rosemary extract are primarily attributed to its rich

content of phenolic acids, flavonoids, and diterpenes. [8] (Fig; 3) Carnosol and carnosic acid account for over 90% of rosemary extract's antioxidant properties. They are potent inhibitors of lipid peroxidation, outperforming propyl gallate, and effectively scavenge peroxy radicals with high-rate constants. Carnosic acid can protect proteins like alpha 1-antiproteinase from HOCl-induced inactivation.

Fig: 3 Antioxidant Mechanism

Both compounds can stimulate DNA damage but also scavenge hydroxyl radicals efficiently. Carnosic acid may also act as a scavenger of H₂O₂ or as a substrate for peroxidase and can reduce cytochrome c, though at a slower rate than O₂ (-). [9] (Fig; 4).

Fig: 4 Free Radical Mechanism of Rosemary

Rosmarinic acid is a phenolic compound derived from the amino acids phenylalanine and tyrosine. Its unique structure features two aromatic rings, one originating from phenylalanine through its conversion to caffeic acid, and the other from tyrosine, which is converted to dihydroxyphenyl-lactic acid. These two pathways come together to form rosmarinic acid, which is known for its strong antioxidant properties. Rosmarinic acid is known for its excellent bioavailability, making it easily absorbed through the gastrointestinal tract and the skin, which enhances its therapeutic potential. Once in the body, it stimulates the production of prostaglandin E₂, a compound that plays a vital role in inflammation regulation and immune response. Additionally, rosmarinic acid

has been shown to decrease the production of leukotriene B₄ in human polymorphonuclear leukocytes, which are key players in inflammatory processes. This modulation of leukotriene levels helps reduce inflammation and related symptoms. Furthermore, rosmarinic acid inhibits the complement system, a part of the immune response that can lead to tissue damage during inflammatory reactions. These multifaceted effects contribute to its potential as an anti-inflammatory agent, making it valuable in treating various inflammatory conditions. Overall, its ability to enhance prostaglandin production while suppressing harmful leukotrienes and complement activity underscores its therapeutic promise. [10] (Fig; 5)

Fig: 5 Anti-inflammatory action of Rosemary

The US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) has classified rosemary extracts as Generally Recognized as Safe (GRAS), and rosemary is deemed safe for consumption in low doses. Experts suggest that safe doses are approximately 400 milligrams per kilogram (mg/kg) of rosemary herb. [11]

Pharmacological Actions Of Rosemary

Rosemary (*R. officinalis* L) belonging to the family Lamiaceae exercises its various pharmacological activity, such as anti-cancer, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, anti-depressant, neuroprotective, and anti-obesity.

Anti-Cancer

A study conducted on various cancer types concluded that rosemary induces anticancer

activity by stopping the activation of carcinogens, increasing antioxidant enzyme activities, reducing tumour-stimulating inflammation, decreasing cell growth, stimulating programmed cell death, and suppressing tumour angiogenesis and invasion. [12]

Antioxidant activity

The antioxidant qualities of rosemary, which are ascribed to phenolic components such as rosmarinic acid and carotene, aid in scavenging reactive oxygen species and averting cell damage caused by oxidative stress. Vitamin stabilization in food and biological systems is another reason for this phenomenon. [14]

PHARMACOLOGICAL ACTIVITY

Anti-obesity

According to previous studies, carnosic acid in rosemary may boost anti-obesity effects by improving lipid profiles, limiting fat absorption, and encouraging good gut bacteria, all of which help lower cholesterol, triglycerides, and weight gain. [15] [16] [17]

Anti-inflammatory

R. officinalis extracts and phytochemicals enhance NSAID ant nociceptive effects by interacting with opioid, 5-HT_{1A}, and TrpV1 receptors, allowing for reduced analgesic doses. Compounds such as carnosic acid and Carnosol also inhibit inflammatory pathways, reduce ROS

levels, and block pain-related channels. [6], [13], [18]

Anti-depressant

Research indicates that by increasing brain dopamine, decreasing corticosterone, and modifying HPA axis function, inhalation of rosemary essential oil can lessen stress. Additionally, it supports neuronal differentiation, neurotransmitter function, and stress-related brain plasticity, indicating that it may be a safe alternative treatment for stress-related mood disorders brought on by stress. [19]

Neuroprotective Action

Studies have validated the efficacy of rosemary in mitigating nervous system illnesses, such as anxiety and Alzheimer's, and in lowering pain in diabetic animals. Furthermore, rosemary extract lowered inflammation and enhanced cognition, suggesting that it may be used as a treatment for age-related and neurodegenerative diseases. Cardio protective Action [20] [21] Carnosol has demonstrated protective properties against acute

cardiotoxicity in rats by lowering oxidative stress, inflammation, and DNA damage, likely through sirtuin-1 activation. Further investigation is required to evaluate its therapeutic potential in particulate-induced cardiotoxicity. [22]

Anti-diabetic

In animal models of type 2 diabetes, rosemary extract and its polyphenols, carnosic acid and rosmarinic acid, have anti-diabetic properties by imitating insulin and lowering hyperglycemia and hyperlipidemia. To verify their processes, bioavailability, and appropriate dosages for the treatment of diabetes, more research—including human trials—is required. [23]

Formulation Studies Involving Rosemary

This section examines contemporary research on the extraction and formulation of rosemary (*Rosmarinus officinalis*) for use in a range of items, including food and cosmetics. These studies demonstrate the bioactive chemicals in rosemary's adaptability and potential to improve product efficacy.

Researched by	Type of formulation	Contains	Application
Alzomor et al [24]	cream and gel	0.5% rosemary extract	Anti-wrinkle therapy.
Kanakidi et al. [25]	Encapsulation method used for solid dosage forms	antioxidant-rich rosemary extracts	food, medicine, and cosmetics
Pinos et a [27]	stevia-and fructan fiber-based jelly candies	rosemary extracts	antioxidant properties, acceptability by consumers, providing a healthier substitute for sugary goods
Francisco José González-Minero,Luis Bravo-Díaz & Antonio Ayala-Gómez [3]	cosmetics	rosemary essential oils	potential to treat androgenic alopecia
Sunil Gupta,Parul Bisht & Shivanand Patil [31]	oil-based gels	Rosemary oil	topical antimicrobial agents

Asia Begum et al [32]	herbal hair lotion	1% methanolic extract of rosemary	to promote hair growth
Cavalcanti J, Silva A & Souza R [33]	soaps	rosemary extracts	antibacterial
Emmanuel Uronnachi et al [34]	oleo gel formulations	10% rosemary oil or 5% rosemary oil	promoted hair growth,

These studies collectively demonstrate the versatility of rosemary as an ingredient in multiple industries. From cosmetic creams and gels to encapsulated supplements and functional foods, rosemary's bioactive compounds offer a range of benefits. The ongoing research and innovative formulations indicate rosemary's growing potential as a natural additive in both pharmaceutical and nutraceutical markets.

Combinations And Synergistic Effects Of Rosemary Extracts

Rosemary (*Rosmarinus officinalis*) has shown significant therapeutic properties on its own; however, its combinations with other natural ingredients enhance and diversify its applications. This section explores various studies that have formulated rosemary with other bioactive compounds, highlighting the synergistic effects achieved.

Combination	Uses/ Benefits
Rosemary and Neem Extracts [35]	Inhibits <i>Malassezia</i> fungus (dandruff-causing), promotes hair growth, improves scalp health, natural alternative to minoxidil
Rosemary and Myrtus Extracts [36]	Stimulates hair growth, reduces hair loss, offers natural alternative with fewer side effects compared to minoxidil
Rosemary and Grapefruit Polyphenols [37]	Provides photoprotection, reduces oxidative damage, improves skin elasticity, promotes anti-aging effects for skin health
Rosemary and Lavender Essential Oils [38]	Reduces joint pain, improves physical function in knee osteoarthritis, effective in pain-relief ointments
Rosemary and Cedarwood Oil [34]	Antibacterial, promotes skin health, provides durability and nourishment in topical gels

Adverse Effects, Side Effects, and Toxicity of Rosemary (*Rosmarinus officinalis*) Although rosemary, or *Rosmarinus officinalis*, has many health benefits, such as anti-inflammatory,

antibacterial, anticancer, neuroprotective, and hepatoprotective qualities, it's crucial to be aware of any possible negative effects and toxicological issues when using larger dosages. [39].

Category	Details
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<p>Toxicology And Dangerous Doses</p>	<p>Neurological Effects: High amounts may lead to symptoms like dizziness, seizures, or confusion. [40] People who are prone to seizures should use rosemary sparingly. [42] Gastrointestinal Issues: Can irritate the digestive system, potentially causing nausea and vomiting. [40] Kidney Toxicity: Prolonged high intake may harm kidney function. [40] Abortifacient Potential: Excessive consumption during pregnancy could risk miscarriage. [40] [42]</p>
<p>Negative Impacts</p>	<p>Allergic Reaction: Rare cases of contact dermatitis, such as a 23-year-old woman who developed erythema after using cosmetics containing rosemary, are examples of allergic reactions. [4] Reproductive Toxicity: Animal studies suggest that male subjects exhibit decreased testosterone levels and reduced reproductive organ weights, while females show diminished fertility. [44] Genotoxicity: Potential effects include the production of apoptotic bodies and DNA fragmentation in developing foetuses. [39]</p>
<p>Precaution And Safety</p>	<p>Nursing: breastfeeding women should take caution [40] [42] Lithium toxicity: risk may increase with alterations in electrolyte balance. Iron uptake may be inhibited, which is particularly concerning for individuals with anaemia. [42] Blood Pressure and Blood Sugar Levels: Those using medications for lowering blood pressure or blood sugar should be cautious, as there may be interactions. [42] Safety: There have been reports of both teratogenic and non-teratogenic effects during pregnancy. It is not advised to use the crude medication on children younger than 12 due to a lack of safety information. [43]</p>

CONCLUSION

Many health benefits of rosemary (*Rosmarinus officinalis*) include its anti-inflammatory and neuroprotective qualities; nonetheless, due diligence in evaluating its safety profile is necessary. Significant toxicological consequences, such as possible genotoxicity and reproductive damage, might result from excessive ingestion, even though the FDA typically considers suggested doses to be safe. As a result of documented allergic responses, people who are

already sensitive should exercise caution. Rosemary is a useful medicinal herb because of its many health advantages and low risk of negative side effects. Rosemary can increase overall effectiveness when mixed with other synthetic or natural substances, particularly when used as an antioxidant. In balanced formulations, the health benefits are enhanced by the synergistic contributions of its active ingredients. Because of its adaptability, the plant can be used in conjunction with a variety of therapies,

contributing both therapeutic and antioxidant benefits. Research points to rosemary's potential as a crucial component of integrated medicine strategies that combine efficacy and safety.

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